

A SENTENCE GENERATION METHOD FOR RULE-BASED LANGUAGES; AN EXAMPLE FROM TURKISH

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Abstract: The most widely used language families today are Altaic, Indo-European, Hami-Semitic and Sino-Tietic. When these language families are evaluated in terms of phonology, morphology and syntax, it is clear that Altaic languages are the most advanced language family. The grammar of languages belonging to the Altaic language family are regular and logical. Due to these features, they are very suitable for artificial intelligence applications. It is difficult to say that Indo-European languages are rule-based like Altaic languages. There are many irregularities in these languages. Therefore, irregular situations must be memorized and sentences must be constructed according to certain patterns. In the first part of this article, the basic grammatical features of Altaic languages were introduced based on Turkish. In the second part of the article, first, it is shown how a sentence can be created using the grammatical features of Turkish language. A program was prepared to test and prove the introduced model and method. The proposed method was tested with this program and the results confirmed the suggestion. The developed method can be used in other Altaic languages with minor adaptations.

Keywords: Natural languages, Alkaic languages, Sentence generating, Vowel harmony, Agglutination, Phonology, Morphology, Syntax, Yapay zeka;

1 Introduction

According to UN reports, the number of languages spoken in the world is around 4000 [1, 2, 3]. However, some of these are spoken by very few people. The most widely spoken language families today are Altaic, Indo-European, Hami-Semitic and Sino-Tibetan. The Altaic language family, which is included in these language families, includes the following languages:

- Turkic languages
 - Chuvash: Chuvash
 - Kipchak: Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Nogay, Karachay, Bashkir, Kumuk, Tatar, Altaic
 - Oghuz: Turkish, Azerbaijani Turkish, Turkmen
 - Uyghur: Uyghur, Uzbek, Salar
 - Yakut: Yakut
- Mongolian languages: Mongolian, Buryat, Kalmyk
- Manchu-Tungus languages: Even, Evenki, Golde, Oroch, Lamut
- Korean
- Japanese

When these three language families are compared in terms of phonology, morphology and syntax, it can be said that the Altaic language family is the most developed language family [4]. The fundamental and common features of Turkic languages are [5]:

- Vowel harmony,
- The absence of gender,
- Agglutination,
- Adjectives precede nouns,
- Verbs come at the end of the sentence.

Vowel harmony, a common feature of Turkic languages, is regular and is shown in the form of a finite state machine in Figure 1. In Turkish, there is also

Fig.1. The FSM representative of vowel harmony of Turkish

harmony between consonants, but this harmony is not as strict as in vowels [6,7].

The Turkic languages in the Altai language family are called agglutinative languages. In agglutinative languages, new words can be derived by adding derivational suffixes to the root of the word. Inflectional suffixes are added to the root word to provide time and person information. The addition of derivational and inflectional suffixes is regular and these rules have never been broken. For this reason, the structures of the Turkic languages are likened to mathematical equations [8]. In the Altai languages, verbs are vectorial, that is, directional indicators (see Figure-2), noun and adjective phrases are very well defined, and case suffixes clearly indicate the status of movements (see Figure-3). Due to these features, the Turkic languages are characterized as logical languages [5].

Fig. 2. *Radyoyu dinliyorum* (accusative) (*I am listening to radio*), *Sana söylüyorum* (dative) (*I am saying something to you*). English verbs do not indicate direction.

English verbs do not indicate direction.

In Turkish languages, the root of a word has a meaning, and derivational suffixes added to the root create new words based on this meaning. The meaning of a new word can be understood by a person by using logic [9,10,11]. In Indo-European languages, a new word must be found for each new concept. For a new word, either dead Latin or ancient Greek dictionaries are scanned. If a suitable word cannot be found in these dictionaries, a new word is created by the cut and paste method, for example, brunch (**breakfast + lunch**). The meaning of the new word created in this way must be memorized. In contrast, in Turkish languages, it is sufficient to know the meaning of the root word. Table-1 provides examples of word derivation in Turkish and English.

Fig. 3. The case suffixes clearly indicate the status of movements

Table 1. The word derivation in Turkish and English

Turkish	English	Class	Turkish	English	Class
Göz	Eye	Noun	Gözlemci	Observer	Adjective
Gözlük	Eyeglasses	Noun	Gözlemcilik	Observation	Noun
Gözlükçü	Optician	Adjective	Gözde	Favourite	Adjective
Gözlükçülük	Opticians	Noun	Gözü	Mirror	Noun
Gözcü	Whachman	Adjective	Gözügölük	Mirror stand	Noun
Gözcülük	Lookout	Noun	Gözügücü	Mirror maker	Adjective
Gözlem	Observation	Noun	Gözügücülük	Mirror makers business	Noun
Gözlemlemek	To observe	Verb	Gözü	Who have eyes	Adjective

The order for adding inflectional suffixes to the nominal root word is shown in Figure 4 [12, 13].

Fig. 4. The order in which inflectional suffixes are added to nominal words

In order for a joint to add the next joint, some adaptations must be made in accordance with the phonetics characteristics of Turkish. In this stage, which we call the merging process,

- vowel consonant harmonies,
- adding fusing letters,
- softening of hard consonants and
- binding vowel harmony rules apply.

The merging process is depicted in Figure-5.

In Turkish, verb conjugation is regular and there are no exceptions. The structure of verb conjugation is seen in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. The Merging process.

Fig.6. The order of suffixes for verb conjugation

Depending on the type of predicate, a verb sentence or a noun sentence can be formed. Sentences written in accordance with the rules of grammar are considered correct sentences. Elements of Turkish sentences can be change position. In this case, there is no significant change in the main meaning of the sentence. Due to this feature, Turkish is considered a language with flexible syntax. In Turkish, compound sentences consisting of more than one sentence can be formed. In the sentence, the complement clause is first followed by the complemented clause. The connection between sentences is established with prepositions, common sentence elements, common person or meaning relations. The structure of Turkish sentence is giving in Figure-7

Fig.7. The structure of Turkish sentence

2 Developed Method

When the literature is scanned, a large number of articles are seen on sentence generation. When these articles are examined, it is seen that most of them were developed for Indo-European languages and therefore probability methods were preferred [14,15,16,17,18,19,20]. No source was found for regular languages.

As seen in Figure 7, the main components of the Turkish sentence are subject, complement (adverb + preposition + complement) and predicate.

Subject: The features of subject are giving below:

The subject can be a living or inanimate entity, a concrete or abstract object.

The subject can be a single word or a phrase.

The subject can be the person doing the job specified by the verb, or it can be the job done.

The subject is attached to the verb without taking any inflectional suffixes other than plural, possessive and genitive suffixes.

There can be more than one subject in a sentence.

One of the subjects in a sentence may undertake the task of explaining the other.

The subject may not appear in some sentences. The subject can be specified with the person suffix of the predicate.

There is no subject in sentences formed with intransitive passive predicates. Predicates are in the third person.

Address elements are considered non-sentence elements because they are connected to the predicate.

This element does not have to agree with the subject in terms of meaning.

It can be the common subject of consecutive sentences.

Nominal words can form subject phrases together.

When the subject is plural, the predicate does not have to be plural as well. If "non-intelligent" beings and objects become subjects, the predicate will be in singular form, even if these subjects exist in plural form.

If the subject is plural and human, the predicate can be singular or plural.

If the subject is singular, the predicate is also singular. If the subject is human and there is more than one (prefixed with any number prefix), the verb is still singular.

The indefinite pronoun and word used instead of a collective noun are also used with the singular form of the predicate:

Compatibility is sought between the subject and the predicate in terms of person.

Phrases that display subject characteristics act as a single word within the sentence.

The order of the words in the phrase is regular. In nominal and nominal phrases, the active word is placed at the end of the phrase, so the auxiliary words are placed before it.

A word phrase can be connected to another phrase by taking a case suffix.

There may also be phrases that complement each other within the phrase that forms the subject.

The phrase that forms the subject can be formed as a noun phrase or an adjective phrase. There are three types of noun phrases in Turkish:

Definite noun phrase

Indefinite noun phrase

Chained noun phrase

The structures of the three forms of noun phrases are given in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. The three forms of noun compound phrases

The structures of the adjective compound phrases are given in Figure 9.

The structure developed to establish the subject is given in Table-2, and a sample result is given as below

A[Ali Ayşe çocuk] OY[güzel sarışın kız] OT[Alpay çirkin kız -] AY[kapı kol] AT[kapı kol] ZCD[han kapı kol]

Fig. 9. The forms of adjective compound phrases

Table 2. **Developed syntax for subject creating**

Input	Output
A[Ali Ayşe çocuk]	Ali Ayşe çocuk
A[Ali Ayşe çocuk] OY[güzel sarışın kız]	Ali Ayşe çocuk güzel sarışın kız
A[Ali çocuk] OT[Alpay güzel kız]	Ali çocuk Alpay'ın güzel kızı
AY[okul yol]	okul yolu
AT[kapı kol]	okulun yolu
OT[Alpay güzel kız -] ATD[kedi gözü]	Alpay'ın güzel kızının kedisinin gözü
ZA[han kapı kol]	han kapı kolu
ZB[han kapı kol]	han kapısının kolu
ZC[han kapı kol]	hanın kapısının kolu
OT[Alpay güzel kız -] ZBD[han kapı kol]	Alpay'ın güzel kızının han kapısının kolu
OT[Alpay güzel kız -] ZBC[han kapı kol]	Alpay'ın güzel kızının hanının kapısının kolu

A: Simple noun, proper noun, object name or pronouns
OY: Prefix phrase
OT: Subjective pronoun phrase: If this phrase qualifies a noun phrase that comes after it, the last element is "-".
AY: Indefinite noun phrase
AT: Definite noun phrase
ATD: Definite noun phrase qualified by the adjective phrase
ZA: Indefinite chained noun phrase
ZB: Chained noun phrase with the last two elements indicated
ZC: Chained noun phrase with all elements indicated.
ZBD: Chained noun phrase with the last two elements

Complement: There are four types of complements in Turkish. The structure of them are depicted in Figure-10.

Direct complement (Object)

Indirect complement

Prepositional phrase

Adverbial phrase

Fig. 10. The structure of complement

The structure developed to establish the complement is given in Table 3. And a sample result is given as below.

NY[kedi köpek] NYA[ağustos böcek] NYO[güzel kuş] NT[kitap dergi] NTA[kapı kol]
 NTO[yakışıklı delikanlı] DTB[Konya Ankara] DTAB[Ankara gar] DTOB[kokulu gül]

Table 3. **Developed syntax for subject creating**

Giriş	Çıkış
NY[kedi köpek]	kedi köpek
NYA[ağustos böcek]	ağustos böceği
NYO[minik kuş]	minik kuş
NT[kitap dergi]	kitabı dergiyi
NTA[kapı kol]	kapının kolunu
NTO[yakışıklı delikanlı]	yakışıklı delikanlıyı
DTY[Konya Ankara]	Konya'ya Ankara'ya
DTD[Konya Ankara]	Konya'da Ankara'da
DTA[Konya Ankara]	Konya'dan Ankara'dan
DTAY[Ankara gar]	Ankara garına
DTAB[Ankara gar]	Ankara garında
DTAA[Ankara gar]	Ankara garından
DTOY[pembe konak]	Pembe konağa
DTOB[pembe konak]	Pembe konakta
DTOA[pembe konak]	Pembe konaktan
BT[hızlı hızlı]	hızlı hızlı
BTA[akşam yedi]	akam yedide
BTO[dün söylemeden]	dün söylemeden
IT[uçak ile]	uçak ile

Predicate: A predicate is

generated according to following rules. Indicative moods, tense and personal inflectional suffixes are shown in Table 4.

- Creating voice suffixes
 - Make a reciprocal
 - Make a reflexive
 - Make causative
 - Make passive
- Compound verbs operations

- Haste
- Competence
- Durative

- Creating the negative of the verb
- Modal operations
- Adding time and person suffixes
- Create the question form

Mode operations are performed by following the following steps. Subjunctive Moods: Tense and person inflectional suffixes are shown in Table 5.

- Edit in verb root
- Creating and combining time and person suffixes
- Softening at the root of verb
- Editing variable letters in verb

Table 4. Indicative Moods: Tense and person Inflectional Suffixes

Tenses	Time suffix	Personel suffixes	Examples
Past tense, indefinite	+mHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevmişim
Past tense	+D	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +Hniz, +HIAr	sevdim
Present simple tense	+(H)yor	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	seviyorum
Future tense	+(y)AcAk	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	seveceğim
Aorist	+(A/H)r *	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +(y)Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	severim
Past perfect tense indefinite	+mHşD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevmiştim
Past perfect tense	+DHyD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevdiydim
Present past tense	+(H)yorD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	seviyordum
Future past time	+(y)AcAkD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevecektim
Aorist perfect tense	+(A/H)rD *	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevdim
Past indefinite Inferential	+mHşmHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevmişmişim
Present Inferential	+(H)yormHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	seviyormuşum
Future Inferential	+(y)AcAkmHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevecekmişim
Aorist Inferential	+(A/H)rmHş *	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	severmişim
Past ind. Inferential conditional	+mHşsA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	sevmişsem
Past ind. Inferential conditional	+DHysA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	sevdiysem
Present conditional	+(H)yorsA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	seviyorsan
Future conditional	+(y)AcAksA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	seveceksem
Aorist conditional	+(A/H)rsA *	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	seversem

Table 5. Subjunctive Moods: Tense and person inflectional suffixes

Moods	Time suffix	Personel suffixes	Examples
Wish - Conditional	+sA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	sevsem
Optative	+A	+yHm +sHn, +""', +IHm, +sHnHz, +IAr	seveyim
Obligational	+mAlH	+yHm, +sHn, +""', +yHz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevmeliyim
Imperative mood	+""'	+""', +""', +sHn, +""', +HnHz, +sHnIAr	sev (2.tek)
Perfect of wish - conditional	+sAyD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevseydim
Perfect of optative	+AyD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevseydim
Perfect of obligational	+mAlHyD	+Hm, +Hn, +H, +Hk, +HnHz, +HIAr	sevmeliydim
Inferential of wish-conditional	+sAymHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevseymişim
Inferential of optative	+AymHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevyemişim
Inferential of obligation	+mAlHymHş	+Hm, +sHn, +""', +Hz, +sHnHz, +IAr	sevmeliymişim
Conditional of obligation	+mAlHysA	+m, +n, +""', +k, +nHz, +IAr	sevmeliysem

Sentence Creation Program: Sentence creation program consists of three components: The program is depicted in Figure-11.

Editor: The editor was developed to allow the user to enter data.

Organizer: In this environment, the elements that should be included in the subject and complement are defined. In addition, it is possible to choose the framework and compound action operations related to the verb root and verb. Naturally, the time, person, positive and negative situations of the action are determined.

In addition to ensuring that definitions and selections can be entered into the program, the editor also checks whether the entries comply with the spelling and logic rules. In this context, it carries out the following inspections.

- Whether or not the fields to be defined and selected have been entered,
- Whether or not there is any character other than the alphabet in the entered words,
- Whether the words entered are Turkish or not,
- Formal control of the spelling of definitions,
- Whether the operators are written correctly and used appropriately,
- Whether all definitions within the subject are made correctly or not,
- Whether all the definitions in the complement are made correctly or not,
- Whether the predicate is Turkish or not,
- Suitability of the options selected for voice operations,
- Suitability of options selected for combined verb,
- Whether the verb mode has been chosen and the appropriateness of the individual's choice for this mode

Interpreter: After entering the necessary information regarding sentence formation, the interpretation phase begins. At this stage, first the definitions entered in the subject and complement fields are analyzed. Within the scope of the analysis process, the definitions entered in the relevant fields are divided into tokens.

A[Eren kedi ben] OY[sarışın kız] OY[güzel kedi] AY[okul yol] OT[Alpay güzel kız] OT[Alpay güzel kız -] ATD[kedi göz] OT[biz büyük ev -] ATD[geniş kapı] ZA[han kapı kol] ZB[han kapı kol]

Fig. 11. Structure of the Sentence Generation Program

The general view of the sentence creation program and an experiment result are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. The general view of the sentence creation program and an experiment result

3 Conclusions

The grammar of the Altaic languages is regular and logical, which allows a sentence to be created according to the rules in these languages. In order to create a sentence, it is sufficient to define the grammatical features of the languages to the program. Since there is no exception to the rule as in Indo-European languages, there is no such thing as introducing exceptions. The sentence creation program presented in the article can create sentences using only the grammatical information of Turkish. The method presented in this article can also be used for other Altaic languages.

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